

Yoga and Mental Peace: A Study

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Abstract At present, Yoga has become widely known and has been used for treatment of chronic health conditions. Through Yoga individuals get empowered positively to take charge of one's own psychological wellness. It could save a large expenditure for treatment and prevention of mental health problems. Yoga can take the form of a new therapy for curative, preventive, protective and promotive objectives at schools, hospitals, health care centers and even in family too. It offers immense help in sustaining wellness, addressing concerns related with increasing suicidal tendencies due to examination anxiety, deal with frustration and conflicts in society and to opt career choices with full awareness of one's own abilities and potentials. Yoga plays a vital role in balancing equilibrium between our mind, body and soul. Hence, the purpose of this study is to analyze how the practice of yoga helps in achieving peace of mind, in comparison with people who do not practice yoga.

Introduction

Yoga is one of the most ancient metaphysical sciences among others. It investigates the nature of soul and through its discipline, awakens the super conscious mind of the man which unites the moral being with the immortal supreme spirit.¹ Human beings suffer from more and more physical and psychological stress and strains and it becomes common among youth of present society. Yoga helps to find out the ways to face them and solve it.

It is very important to mention that Yoga creates balance and also provides both a philosophy and a religion. The real joy of life appears when we can unify nature and culture, wealth and poverty, movement and stillness, attachment and detachment. In this respect, the yogic activities provide immense help in assisting an individual to seek his all round growth and development in all the personality dimensions including the union of his self with the Greater soul. Many still believe that yoga is a religion, but it's not, instead, it's a way of living who strives to have a healthy mind in a healthy body. A human is a mental, physical and spiritual being and yoga helps promote a balanced development of all the three. Other forms of physical exercises, such as aerobics, guarantee only physical well being. They have very little to do with the development of the spiritual or planetary body.

Yoga is a form of mind-body fitness that involves a combination of muscular activity and an internally directed mindful focus on awareness of the self, the breath, and energy. Four basic

principles underlie the teachings and practices of yoga's healing system.² The first principle is the human body is a holistic entity comprised of various interrelated dimensions inseparable from one another and the health or illness of any one dimension affects the other dimensions. The second principle is individuals and their needs are unique and therefore must be approached in a way that acknowledges this individuality and their practice must be tailored accordingly. The third principle is yoga is self-empowering; the student is his or her own healer. Yoga engages the student in the healing process; by playing an active role in their journey toward health, the healing comes from within, instead of from an outside source and a greater sense of autonomy is achieved. The fourth principle is that the quality and state of an individual's mind is crucial to healing. When the individual has a positive mind-state healing happens more quickly, whereas if the mind-state is negative, healing may be prolonged.

In recent years there is a growing utilization of Yoga as one of the therapeutic measure in the field of mental health where the benefits of yoga practice and therapy are being widely recognized. Now the health professionals are aware of therapeutic values of yoga and many introduce the approach as a psycho-physiologic and spiritual technique in their treatment.³ Research indicate

¹ Shyam Sundar Sarkar (2018) "Yoga And It's Importance In Our Daily Life", *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention (IJHSSI)*, Volume 7 Issue 08 Ver. II, ISSN- 2319 – 7722, P.48.

² Catherine Woodyard, (2011) "Exploring the therapeutic effects of yoga and its ability to increase quality of life", *international journal of Yoga*, Issue No- 4(2): 49–54, retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/article/PMC3193654/>

³ Shankar Das (2018) "Global Mental Health, Peace and Sustainability: Does Yoga Show the Way?",

Asanas increase patient's physical flexibility, strength and coordination while the Pranayama and Meditation practices calm and focus the mind to enhance higher self awareness and lessen anxiety, that result in better quality of patients life. Some other beneficial and therapeutic effects reported by Yang such as reduction in level of distress, blood pressure, and improvement in mood, resilience and metabolic regulation. Studies also indicate yoga is effective in the treatment of anxiety disorders (including in caregivers), pain, Alzheimer's disease, stroke prevention and rehabilitation, epilepsy, peripheral nervous system disorders and multiple sclerosis. Hence, this study is an effort to understand how Yoga could bring mental peace in our life.

Objective

1. To understand how Yoga could bring mental peace in our life.
2. To know the importance of Yoga in balancing equilibrium between our mind, body and soul.

Methodology

This study is primarily descriptive and analytical. In this study only secondary source of data have been used. The secondary source of data includes like books, articles, research papers, report published from various sources, internet sources and so on.

History of Yoga

The history of yoga is indeed very old and nothing can be said firmly about the origin of yoga only it can be alluded that yoga was organized in India. The available evidence shows that history of yoga was related to Indus valley civilization. At that time people used to do yoga. On the basis of various sculptures and sculptures we reach at the conclusion that yoga was a part of the civilization. Yoga has its origins in ancient Indian philosophy and can be traced back to the Rigveda itself, the oldest Hindu text which speaks about yoking our mind and insight to the Light of Truth or Reality. Great teachers of early Yoga include the names of many famous Vedic sages like Vāsiṣṭha, Yajñavalkya, and Jaigīśavya. The greatest of the Yogis is always said to be Yogeśvara Kṛṣṇa himself, the propounder of Bhagavadgītā which is called as Yoga Śāstra an authoritative work on Yoga. Lord Śiva is also the greatest of the Yogis or Ādinātha.

The word "Yoga" originates from Sanskrit and it means "to join, to unite". Yoga exercises have a holistic effect and bring body, mind, consciousness and soul into balance. Yoga assists us in coping with everyday demands, problems and worries.⁴ It also helps to develop a greater understanding of our self, the purpose of life and our relationship to God. On the spiritual path, Yoga leads us to supreme knowledge and eternal bliss in the union of the individual Self with the universal Self. Yoga is that supreme, cosmic principle. It is the light of life, the universal creative consciousness that is always awake and never sleeps; that always was, always is, and always will be.

It needs to mention here that Yoga is a 5000 year old tradition. In India monks went into seclusion for years with the goal of creating a disease free strong body. The original intention was to be able to sit in meditation for hours but with a achy body that is impossible to do.

In India, Yoga has been part of man's activities directed towards higher spiritual achievements. The history of Yoga could be divided into five categories: a. Vedic period b. Pre-classical period c. Classical period d. Yoga in Medieval Times e. Yoga in Modern Times. All these five categories of Yoga could be discussed as follows-

Vedic period: The earliest recorded mention of the word 'yoga' is in the ancient Indian text, the Rig Veda - this body of knowledge dates back to around 1500 BC! In the Atharva Veda, again (dating to 1200-1000 BC), there is a mention of the importance of the control of breath. It is difficult to pinpoint exact dates because in the beginning, the Vedas were, only, orally passed on from one generation to another. Written records came much later.⁵

Pre-classical period: In this period, the Upanishads took birth. They explain the meaning hidden in the Vedas, elaborating on the workings of the mind and spirit through personal teachings. They espouse meditation and mantra recitation towards the ultimate goal of attaining enlightenment. Out of the 108 Upanishads, there are 20 yoga Upanishads.

⁴ Sunil Kumar Yadav, Ashwani Kumar, Vikas Kumar, Anil Kumar (2015) "Importance of yoga in daily life", retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278673574>

⁵ See A brief history of yoga: Through the ages available at <https://www.artofliving.org/in-en/yoga/yoga-for-beginners/brief-history-yoga>.

Classical period: In the classical period, Lord Mahavira and Lord Buddha's teachings formed the early basis for Yoga Sadhana. While Lord Mahavira spoke of attaining salvation and freedom through meditation, Lord Buddha spoke of specific postures and meditation to attain enlightenment. The Bhagavad Gita also came into existence in this period. This text is a dialogue between Lord Krishna (universal consciousness) and Prince Arjuna (human consciousness). Here, the Lord explains the concepts of Dharma, Karma yoga (generous actions), Bhakti yoga (dedicated and caring actions) and Jnana yoga (knowledge).

Yoga in Medieval Times: With regard to Yoga in Medieval times, many sages and philosophers such as Adi Shankaracharya contributed to the development and continuation of Raja Yoga and Jnana yoga, adopting and building upon the teachings and techniques of yoga. With his teachings, and yogic rituals, like the Jnana Yoga, one can achieve Nirvana or liberation. Additionally, meditation was also considered vital to help clear the mind.

Yoga in Modern Times: There are numerous person and instances associated with the development of Yoga in Modern times. Swami Vivekananda was largely responsible for the spread of yoga to western societies. Here, there was much focus on physical well-being. Raja yoga was further developed by Ramana Maharshi, Ramakrishna Paramahansa, BKS Iyengar, K Pattabhi Jois, Paramhansa Yogananda, and Vivekananda. Yoga spread to the West in the mid-nineteenth century. Vedanta, Bhakti and Hatha yoga flourished at this time.

These are the five categories through which one can understand about the historical background of Yoga. However, many more things left out from this discussion.

Yoga and Mental Peace

The practice of yoga has grown as a universal science which has innumerable therapeutic facets that helps to achieve holistic health. Though there are numerous types and schools of yoga, each characterizes their own specific styles of mind and body postures (asanas), breathing techniques (pranayama), meditation and deep relaxation practices that fosters awareness and eventually promote intense states of consciousness. According to yoga the nervous system of an individual affects one's health and yoga purifies and brings relaxation to the mind. It symbolizes

unification of mind, body and soul to enable a person to gain higher consciousness.

In the Indian tradition, Yoga was conceived as a pathway towards attainment of joy in life, freedom from sorrows, mental balance and peace. Since antiquity, the seekers of self-realization (often called as Rishis or Yogis) have been using yogic practices for restoring mind-body balance in order to make them capable for attaining spiritual realization.⁶ The ultimate states of human mental health development have been described using different terms. For example, Buddhists use notion of 'Nirvana', Samkhya system uses 'Moksha', Vedantists use 'Atmasakshaatkar' etc. But all these notions converge in their meanings that it involves liberation from suffering. Sage Patanjali, who collated, coordinated and systematized the system of Yoga, declared the main objective of Yoga as regulation of mind in the first aphorism of famous Yoga Sutra (Yogah Chittvritti Nirodhah). Bhagavad Gita, which elaborates comprehensive typologies of Yoga, also states the need of Yoga for removing sorrow and increasing bliss in life. Hath Yoga, a yogic tradition focusing on physical modus-operandi for realizing deeper states of consciousness, emphasises on postures, breathing patterns, energy locks and contemplation to enhance energy and vitality.

Mental health is very important for quality life of an individual. Promoting mental health is crucial to raise performance and enhancing the quality of life and health. By fostering psychological health, several social problems can be addressed effectively. Yoga, which has immense capacity to promote mental health, has not been used to cater to the needs of mental health promotion.⁷ It can empower people to self-regulate their emotions, behaviors and cognitive processes. Regular practice of Yoga may decreases the time taken to fall asleep, increase in the total number of sleep hours, and feeling of being fresh after sleep in the morning. Although the practice of Yoga only cannot be complete cure for many chronic ailments but it can uplift patient's mood and therefore play an important role in the management of wellness in patients suffering with different critical illnesses. Among cancer patients, for instance, it can

⁶ Arun Pratap Singh (2017) "Yoga for mental health: opportunities and challenges", *MOJ Yoga & Physical Therapy*, Volume 2 Issue 1, p.1.

⁷ Ibid

increase acceptance of life in reality, energy, relaxation, quality of sleep and quality of life.

It is very crucial to mention that creating sustainable global peace on the Earth is an ultimate state of contentment and freedom amongst and within all nations and humanity.⁸ At the same time sporadic and acute societal unrest; including religious fanaticism, terrorism, territorial disputes, political and ethnic tensions posing greater challenge of the era around the globe. The interpersonal conflict may escalate to institutional aggression, hostility and war. For every human being world peace is desirable and peace brings both material and spiritual benefit to all societies. When it's most needed the yogic science has the power to inspire grassroots social change in the world. Yoga is not just for self-transformation, but is an instrument for global peace which provides internal, emotional and spiritual reconciliation and healing. It gives one the self-strength and capability to approach conflicts from a space of mindfulness, compassion and love, in such circumstances peace is inevitable.

Conclusion

Currently, Yoga become popular all over the world and now it is being practiced by citizens of all the continents. Indeed Yoga has become widely known and has been used for treatment of chronic health conditions, and management of the symptoms related to acute physical ailments. Yoga empowers individuals' positively to take charge of their own psychological wellness and save a large expenditure for treatment and prevention of mental health problems. Yoga can take the form of a new therapy for curative, preventive, protective and promotive objectives at schools, hospitals, health care centers and in family. It offers immense help in sustaining wellness, addressing concerns related with increasing suicidal tendencies due to examination anxiety, deal with frustration and conflicts in society and to opt career choices with full awareness of one's own abilities and potentials. After going through this discussion it can be said that Yoga is very important not only to maintain good physical health but also mental health too. However, it needs to mention that the common masses of India are yet to understand about the benefit of Yoga. To make it success,

government should take proper policies and needs to introduce some courses in the School, College and also in University level for popularizing it.

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⁸ Shankar Das (2018) "Global Mental Health, Peace and Sustainability: Does Yoga Show the Way?", *Journal of Depression and Anxiety*, Volume 7, Issue 1, 2167-1044, p.2.